

Syngas production via Biomass Chemical Looping Gasification (BCLG) in a 50 kW_{th} unit using ilmenite as oxygen carrier

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Abstract

The use of liquid biofuels is considered one of the most relevant ways to achieve the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the sector of transport, and more specifically in aviation. A possible route is the use of biogenic waste from the agriculture and forestry sector to obtain synthesis gas via gasification and then the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis to obtain liquid biofuels. Among the different technologies available for the gasification process, Biomass Chemical Looping Gasification (BCLG) represents an innovative process that allows the generation of non-nitrogen diluted synthesis gas under autothermic conditions and with low tars content. By using carbon-neutral biomass as fuel, even net negative emissions could be achieved if the BCLG process is combined with CO₂ storage.

This work presents an experimental campaign of 40 hours of continuous operation in a 50 kW_{th} BCLG unit developed inside the EU H2020 CLARA Project. Wheat straw pellets with additives were used as fuel feedstock and ilmenite as solid oxygen carrier. This work aimed to investigate the effect of different operational variables such as the fuel reactor temperature, the mean residence time of solids in the fuel reactor, the oxygen-to-biomass ratio (controlled by the oxygen fed into the air reactor) and the gas velocity in the carbon stripper, on the process performance and the syngas yield. Unlike previous studies, effective oxygen-to-biomass ratios that consider the right amount of oxygen that reacts with the oxygen carrier both in the fuel and air reactors ($\lambda_{eff,FR}$ and $\lambda_{eff,AR}$, respectively) were defined

The main factor affecting the syngas yield and the cold gas efficiency was $\lambda_{eff,FR}$, since it represents the amount of lattice oxygen that actually reacts in the fuel reactor during syngas combustion. However, it showed a low impact on the production of light hydrocarbons (CH₄ and C₂-C₃). The temperature and mean residence time in the fuel reactor showed a considerable effect on the char conversion in the fuel reactor, since an increase in those factors caused an increase in the reaction rates or in the contact time between the oxygen carrier and biomass in the fuel reactor, respectively.

Finally, the carbon stripper did not show the ability to separate the solid oxygen carrier from the unconverted char entrained from the fuel reactor, as the char still retained its initial pellet form. Therefore, an increase in gas velocity of carbon stripper promoted the char by-pass to the air reactor, increasing both the biomass conversion in the unit and the fraction of carbon emitted in the air reactor.

Keywords: Biomass, Chemical Looping Gasification, Syngas, Ilmenite.

1. Introduction

The reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the sectors of transport, industry and electricity generation continues to be one of the main objectives to mitigate the effects of climate change. Although other options have been considered, the use of liquid biofuels in the transport sector is considered one of the most relevant ways to achieve this target. A possible route is the use of biogenic waste from the agriculture and forestry sectors to obtain synthesis gas via gasification and then the Fischer Tropsch (FT) synthesis to obtain liquid biofuels. Among the different technologies available for the gasification process, Biomass Chemical Looping Gasification (BCLG) represents an innovative process that allows the generation of non-nitrogen diluted synthesis gas under autothermic

conditions and with low tars content. By using carbon-neutral biomass as fuel, even net negative emissions could be achieved if the BCLG process is combined with CO₂ storage. In summary, BCLG has several advantages compared to conventional gasification technologies.

In the fuel reactor, biomass is dried and devolatilized, generating gases (mainly hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methane, and light hydrocarbons), tars and char. Char is gasified by H₂O or CO₂, which are used as both fluidizing media and gasifying agent. Gaseous products may be partially oxidized by the oxygen carrier. Thus, solid fuel is converted to synthesis gas and the oxygen carrier is reduced in parallel. In the air reactor, the reduced oxygen carrier is regenerated with air to begin a new cycle. In addition, the oxygen carrier is responsible for transporting the heat required for the endothermic reactions that occur in the fuel reactor from the air reactor where heat is generated due to exothermic reactions.

The objective of this work was to investigate the effect of the main operating variables on the process behavior and syngas generation, including the gasification temperature in the fuel reactor, the oxygen-to-biomass ratio and the gas flow to the carbon stripper.

This work was carried out inside the EU H2020 CLARA Project and reports 40 hours of continuous operation in a 50 kW_{th} BCLG unit located at ICB-CSIC (Spain) using wheat straw pellets with additives as fuel feedstock. Ilmenite was selected as oxygen carrier due to its appropriate characteristics for the process, such as high mechanical strength, low agglomeration tendency, and being environmentally friendly [1]. This ore has also shown a good behavior in previous continuous operation studies carried out in a 1.5 kW_{th} BCLG unit [2].

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The ilmenite used in this study was a concentrate from a Norwegian natural ore from Titania AS [3]. It was received in its reduced form, FeTiO₃, and it was crushed and sieved to obtain a sand-type material with particle size of +100-300 μm. Before its use in the continuous units at CSIC, fresh ilmenite particles were pre-oxidized to pseudobrookite (Fe₂TiO₅) in air at 950 °C during 24 hours to improve the physical properties and initial reaction rates [4] and to avoid defluidization problems [5]. The composition of calcined ilmenite determined by XRD analysis was 54.7 wt% Fe₂TiO₅, 11.2 wt% Fe₂O₃, 28.6 wt% TiO₂ and 5.5 wt% of inert compounds. The oxygen transport capacity for the calcined ilmenite (R_{O,ilm}), was 4.03 wt%.

Pellets of wheat straw biomass with additives supplied by CENER (Pamplona, Spain) (6 mm diameter and 17 mm length, density of 1060 kg/m³) were used as renewable solid fuel. Table 1 shows the proximate and ultimate analysis of the biomass.

Table 1. Analyses of the wheat straw pellets with additives (as received).

Proximate analysis (wt.%)	
Moisture	13.3
Ash	6.2
Volatile matter	69.8
Fixed carbon	13.7
Ultimate analysis (wt.%)	
C	41.4
H*	5.1
N	0.4
S	0.1
O (by difference)	36.4
Lower Heating Value (kJ/kg)	17200

* H does not include hydrogen in H₂O

2.2. Biomass Chemical Looping Gasification unit

Figure 1 shows the scheme of the 50 kW_{th} BCLG unit located at ICB-CSIC, that consist of two interconnected fluidized bed reactors, fuel (FR) and air (AR) reactors, with the oxygen carrier circulating between them. The carbon stripper (CS) has the purpose of separating the unconverted char in the fuel reactor from the oxygen carrier particles. Thus, char passing to the air reactor is minimized while char conversion in the fuel reactor is improved. The loop-seals avoid the gas mixing between the reactors. The biomass is fed to the fuel reactor by means of two screw feeders and a cyclone is used to separate the gas from the solids at the outlet of each reactor. More detailed information can be found in the study conducted by Abad et al. [6].

In addition, the unit includes a system of pressure and temperature sensors distributed throughout the unit. This allows knowing the pressure difference between different points, being mainly useful for the quantification of the amount of solids present in each reactor.

The gas composition at the air reactor outlet stream (CO₂, CO, and O₂) was analyzed in an on-line gas analyser. The gas composition at the fuel reactor outlet (CO₂, CO, H₂, and CH₄) was also measured on-line after gas cleaning, which consisted of a tar collection system installed according to the European Tar Protocol [7]. Moreover, off-line gas analyses were carried out in a gas chromatograph to determine the amount of light hydrocarbons (C₁-C₃) contained in the gas outlet stream of the fuel reactor.

The solids circulation rate may be controlled by the gas velocity into the air reactor or operating on the double loop-seal (LS-D). Its measurement was made at the outlet of both reactors by means of two solids diverter valves. The oxygen carrier inventory at the facility was kept constant at about 75 kg. Steam was used as fluidizing gas in the fuel reactor and a mixture of nitrogen and air was used in the air reactor. The carbon-stripper and the loop-seals were fluidized with N₂. The method of control of the oxygen used for the syngas production was based on controlling the amount of oxygen fed into the air reactor by diluting air with nitrogen. This led to the presence of highly reduced states of the oxygen carrier inside the unit.

Figure 1. Scheme of the 50 kW_{th} BCLG unit at ICB-CSIC.

The operating variables with the greatest impact on the BCLG process performance and syngas production are the gasification temperature and the oxygen-to-biomass ratio, λ , [2,8,9] the later representing the oxygen fed into the air reactor with respect to the stoichiometric oxygen needed to fully burn the biomass.

$$\lambda = \frac{\text{mol O fed to the AR}}{\text{mol O needed for full biomass combustion}} \quad (1)$$

However, the oxygen transferred to the oxygen carrier in the air reactor and to the fuel in the fuel reactor may differ from the oxygen fed in air because some oxygen may react with by-passed char to the air reactor, decreasing the available oxygen to react with the oxygen carrier. Also, the oxygen transferred in the fuel and air reactors may be different during transitory periods prior to the establishment of the steady state. To know the oxygen transferred in the air and fuel reactors at any moment, the effective oxygen-to-biomass ratios in the air, $\lambda_{eff,AR}$, and fuel, $\lambda_{eff,FR}$, reactors were defined.

$$\lambda_{eff,AR} = \frac{\text{mol O picked up by the oxygen carrier in the AR}}{\text{mol O needed for full biomass combustion}} \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_{eff,FR} = \frac{\text{mol O released by the oxygen carrier in the FR}}{\text{mol O needed for full biomass combustion}} \quad (3)$$

The mean residence time of the solid oxygen carrier in the fuel reactor, $t_{m,FR}$, was also a relevant operating variable in the process. This was defined considering the solids circulation rate between the two reactors and the solids inventory in the fuel reactor. The later was calculated from the pressure measurements that were monitored in the fuel reactor.

$$t_{m,FR} = \frac{\text{solids inventory in the FR (kg)}}{\text{solids circulation rate (kg/s)}} \quad (4)$$

2.3. Data evaluation

The performance of the BCLG unit was evaluated based on the following parameters:

- The biomass conversion, X_b , is defined as the amount of carbon contained in the biomass that is converted into gas, both in the fuel and air reactors.
- The char conversion in the fuel reactor, $X_{char,FR}$, represents the fraction of fixed carbon converted to gas in the fuel reactor over the total fixed carbon fed.
- The carbon conversion efficiency, η_{CC} , indicates the fraction of the carbon converted to gas in the fuel reactor relative to the total carbon converted to gas in the fuel and air reactors.
- The syngas yield, Y_{syngas} , shows the amount of H_2 and CO produced over the amount of dry biomass fed into the system, expressed in Nm^3/kg of dry biomass.
- The cold gas efficiency, η_g , is the fraction of chemical energy contained in the product gas from the fuel reactor over the total energy of the biomass fed into the system.

3. Results

The effect of different operating conditions on the performance of the process and the syngas yield was analyzed in this work. The experimental campaign covers about 40 hours of continuous operation in a 50 kW_{th} BCLG unit using ilmenite as oxygen carrier and wheat straw pellets with additives as fuel. Steam was fed as gasifying agent into the fuel reactor with a steam-to-biomass ratio of 0.7 kg/kg dry biomass. The most relevant variables affecting to the CLG process were the gasification temperature and the solids residence time in the fuel reactor, the oxygen-to-biomass ratio (controlled by the oxygen fed to the air reactor), and the gas velocity in the carbon stripper. All of them have a significant effect on the process performance although having different effects depending on the evaluated parameter.

As an example, Figure 2 shows the composition and main parameters for selected tests carried out at 980 °C under different operating conditions. It can be observed that similar syngas compositions were obtained at different operating conditions, although the performance parameters were different. The reason for such differences will be commented later in the manuscript.

Figure 2. Composition and main results obtained for selected BCLG tests. T=980 °C.

3.1. Effect of temperature and mean residence time in the fuel reactor

It is well known that temperature affects to the reaction rates present in any process. To carry out this evaluation, the gasification temperature was varied in the usual range of gasification processes (800-980 °C). A previous work carried out by our research group with ilmenite in the BCLG process at 1.5 kW_{th} scale showed that temperature had little effect on syngas composition [2]. Similar results were also observed using other type of materials based on Fe and Mn as oxygen carrier in continuous operation [8]. However, both the char gasification rate and syngas yield were affected by reacting temperature.

Figure 3 shows the effect of temperature and mean residence time of the oxygen carrier in the fuel reactor on char conversion. Conversion of char in the fuel reactor increased with the mean residence time of the oxygen carrier, $t_{m,FR}$. This fact suggested that the residence time of char particles in the fuel reactor was affected by the solids circulation rate of the oxygen carrier. The size of the biomass pellets used in this work was quite large, and entrainment of the char to the cyclone would not be expected considering the gas velocity in the fuel reactor. However, entrainment of pellets were evident after an examination of the solids exiting the fuel reactor cyclone; see Figure 4. A more detailed evaluation of solids leaving the fuel reactor did not show the presence of a significant amount of char in the form of powder; thus, pelletized biomass retained the initial cylindrical shape of the biomass pellets after its partial gasification in the fuel reactor. Therefore, it was concluded that the entrainment of oxygen carrier particles promotes the entrainment of large char particles.

In addition, an increase in temperature led to an increase in char conversion for a given solids residence time. For example, in order to have char conversion values as high as 70-80% in the fuel reactor, the mean residence time of solids in the fuel reactor should be 300-400 s at 910 °C.

Figure 3. Effect of temperature and mean residence time on char conversion in the fuel reactor.

Figure 4. Unconverted char on the fuel reactor, carbon stripper and air reactor.

The fate of unconverted carbon in the fuel reactor is uncertain. CO_2 was observed in the exhaust gases from the air reactor in some tests. This means that some unconverted char particles reached the air reactor and were burned in contact with the gaseous oxygen, reducing the carbon conversion efficiency, η_{CC} , of the process. The sample taken from the carbon stripper showed that some of the non-gasified pelletized char was being accumulated there; see Figure 4. Note that N_2 was used as fluidizing gas in the carbon stripper. This gas was selected instead of H_2O or CO_2 –which would be used in an industrial process– to prevent the gasification of the char in the carbon stripper and to facilitate the interpretation of the results obtained in the CLG facility. Neither char nor oxygen carrier particles were entrained from the carbon stripper into the fuel reactor; see Figure 1 for the unit configuration. Therefore, the carbon stripper did not have a relevant function when pelletized biomass was used as fuel. However, no char pellets were found in the sample taken from the air reactor. Only a small amount of powdered char was observed, suggesting that the char reaching the air reactor was quickly consumed by combustion.

The biomass conversion in the CLG unit varied between 60 and 100% in all tests of the experimental campaign. The total carbon conversion in the unit was affected by temperature, since it directly depends on the char conversion in the fuel reactor. At lower temperatures, the lower reaction rates in the fuel reactor caused char accumulation in the fuel reactor, which reduced $X_{char,FR}$ and consequently lower values of X_b were obtained. Unconverted char did not escape in any relevant amount from the cyclones downstream of the fuel and air reactors. Therefore, it is believed that carbon was being accumulated in the carbon stripper. The following tests were carried out to confirm this assumption.

3.2. Effect of the gas flow fed to the carbon stripper (CS)

Another variable studied in this work was the gas flowrate fed to the carbon stripper. The carbon stripper was designed for powdered fuels, which may be easily separated from the oxygen carrier particles due to their differences on size and density; thus, unconverted char particles may be entrained to the fuel reactor by controlling the gas velocity in the carbon stripper [6]. However, the behavior with pelletized biomass may be different than with powdered fuels.

It was observed that an increase in the CS gas velocity increased the amount of unconverted char from the fuel reactor reaching the air reactor. Coming into contact with the oxygen present in the air reactor, the combustion of the char occurred, causing an increase in the CO₂ concentration and decreasing the carbon conversion efficiency, η_{cc} . This was observed in tests showed in Figure 2, where an increase in the u_{CS} from 14 (Test 1) to 35 cm/s (Test 2-3) produced a decrease in η_{cc} from 90% to 80.6% and 75.8%, respectively. Eventually, the biomass conversion in the CLG unit reached values close to 100% with the highest gas velocity tested in the carbon stripper (Tests 2-3 in Figure 2). This indicated that there was no char buildup on the unit, as well as no significant char elutriation. In addition, no increase in char conversion was observed in the fuel reactor (Tests 1-2 in Figure 2), indicating that the unconverted char leaving the fuel reactor was not separated from the oxygen carrier in the carbon stripper and was not recirculated to the fuel reactor. In conclusion, although the biomass conversion increased considerably, the carbon capture efficiency, η_{CC} , was reduced.

3.3. Effect of the oxygen-to-biomass ratio

It is known that the oxygen-to-fuel ratio, λ , is the most relevant operating variable affecting the syngas yield, since it represents the amount of oxygen used for gasification/combustion and, therefore, the degree of partial combustion of the gasification products. In addition to its impact on the quality of the synthesis gas, this variable is crucial for the objective of achieving autothermal operating conditions in the system. In this work, this parameter was varied by controlling the air flow to the air reactor, diluting the air with N₂, which demonstrated to be an easy and accurate control method in operating BCLG units. A previous work carried out by our research group showed that the optimal value of λ to achieve the autothermal BCLG process with the higher syngas quality varied between 0.33 and 0.38 [9]. An increase in λ values led to an increase in CO₂ content and lower syngas yields.

In this work, two new parameters were used to consider the correct amount of oxygen that reacts with the oxygen carrier in the fuel and air reactors, $\lambda_{eff,AR}$ and $\lambda_{eff,FR}$, respectively. These effective oxygen-to-biomass ratios should be equal when steady state is reached ($\Phi = \lambda_{eff,FR} / \lambda_{eff,AR} = 1$). Moreover, its value under steady state conditions should be less than λ , since part of the oxygen fed to the air reactor could react with the char coming from the fuel reactor instead of being used for ilmenite oxidation.

Transitory periods were observed in the CLG unit when some operating condition was varied. Figure 5 shows points where the steady state has not been reached as the effective transfer of oxygen in the fuel reactor was lower ($\Phi < 1$) or higher ($\Phi > 1$) than the oxygen transferred in the air reactor to the oxygen carrier. For example, $\Phi < 1$ values were observed when the air flow, and therefore λ , was suddenly increased in the air reactor. In this case, the highly reduced ilmenite reacted with the excess of oxygen but it took some time to transfer it to the fuel reactor. In contrast, $\Phi > 1$ values were often evidenced when the solids circulation rate decreased due to a transitory lack of oxygen in the fuel reactor while solids in the air reactor reached a higher oxidation degree. Temperature changes may also affect to the Φ value at the beginning of the operation. For example, an increase in temperature means that a greater amount of char is being gasified, either due to an increase in the gasification rate or to an excess of char caused by previous accumulation. Therefore, there is a higher oxygen demand in the fuel reactor due to the increased fuel conversion that was initially taken from the accumulated lattice oxygen and consumed in the fuel reactor.

Figure 5. Relationship between effective oxygen-to-biomass ratios in fuel and air reactors, $\lambda_{eff,AR}$ and $\lambda_{eff,FR}$, respectively. Solids points represent steady state conditions. Empty points represent transitory states.

Among the three oxygen-to-biomass ratio defined by equations (1), (2) and (3), the effective oxygen-to-biomass ratio in the fuel reactor, $\lambda_{eff,FR}$, had a direct influence on the syngas yield. Figure 6 shows the effect of $\lambda_{eff,FR}$ on the syngas yield for different values of char conversion obtained in the fuel reactor. For a given char conversion value in the fuel reactor, an increase in the ratio $\lambda_{eff,FR}$ caused a decrease in the syngas yield since a part of the syngas produced was burnt to CO_2 and H_2O . As a consequence ilmenite released a larger amount of lattice oxygen in the fuel reactor. Thus, the concentration of CO_2 increased while the concentration of H_2 and CO decreased.

In addition, it was observed that the temperature and the mean residence time of solids in the fuel reactor were not variables with a direct effect on the syngas yield, but rather on the conversion of char in the fuel reactor, $X_{char,FR}$. Obviously, temperature and solids residence time had a direct effect on char conversion, as shown in Figure 3. For example, considering the results showed in Figure 2, a decrease in $t_{mr,FR}$ from 124 s (Test 2) to 53 (Tests 3) produced a decreased in $X_{char,FR}$ from 41 to 16, respectively, while the syngas was maintained in values about $0.65 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{kg}$.

Figure 6. Effect of the effective oxygen-to-biomass ratio in the FR, $\lambda_{eff,FR}$, on the syngas yield, Y_{syngas} , and yield to HCs Y_{HCs} , for different char conversions in the FR, $X_{char,FR}$.

The cold gas efficiency, η_g , was another parameter affected by the oxygen-to-biomass ratio, since it also depends directly on the syngas composition. By decreasing the syngas quality, its calorific value is also reduced. This trend was also observed in previous studies at the 1.5 kW_{th} scale based on the same oxygen control method as the one used in this work [2,8], as well as in other research based on the biomass-feeding variation for controlling oxygen [10,11].

On the other hand, it can be seen in Figure 5 that the yield to light hydrocarbons (CH₄ and C₂-C₃ from biomass devolatilization), Y_{HCS} , was hardly affected by the variation in the ratio $\lambda_{eff,FR}$. In fact, Abad et al. [12] found a low reactivity of ilmenite with CH₄. In CLG, the conditions of the fuel reactor are deficient in oxygen and it was likely to react mainly with H₂ and CO in the syngas rather than with light hydrocarbons. There was also no clear effect of the char conversion in the fuel reactor on the production of light hydrocarbons. Thus, the results obtained in previous works during continuous operation in a 1.5 kW_{th} BCLG unit, where the amount of HCs were hardly affected by the amount of lattice oxygen transported to the fuel reactor [2,8], were corroborated in this work.

4. Conclusions

The use of ilmenite as oxygen carrier for the BCLG process was investigated for 40 h using wheat straw pellets with additives as fuel in a 50 kW_{th} unit. Ilmenite showed a good behavior, being feasible to obtain non-diluted nitrogen syngas with high values of CO₂ capture.

Temperature showed a major impact on the char conversion of the fuel reactor, $X_{char,FR}$, as an increase in temperature increased the reaction rates of all the reactions occurring in the gasification reactor. An increase in the mean residence time of solids also led to increased char conversion values.

Char conversion in the fuel reactor was not enhanced by the presence of the carbon stripper. The carbon stripper was not capable of separating the unconverted char entrained from the fuel reactor, because it still retains its initial pellet form. Increasing the gas feed rate improved the biomass conversion in the unit, X_b , while the carbon conversion efficiency in the CLG unit, η_{CC} , was reduced because the char by-pass to the air reactor was promoted.

The oxygen-to-biomass ratio, λ , was the most relevant operating variable affecting syngas production. However, depending on the operating conditions, this variable did not consider the exact amount of oxygen that reacted with the oxygen carrier in both fuel and air reactors. Therefore, the effective oxygen-to-biomass ratios were used, $\lambda_{eff,FR}$ and $\lambda_{eff,AR}$, respectively. These parameters helped us to know when the steady state had been reached ($\Phi = \lambda_{eff,FR} / \lambda_{eff,AR} = 1$) under certain operating conditions. An increase in the ratio $\lambda_{eff,FR}$ caused a decrease in the syngas yield and the cold gas efficiency as more syngas was consumed in combustion, as more lattice oxygen reacted in the fuel reactor. Finally, it was observed that the variation of λ had low impact on the production of CH₄ and light hydrocarbons.

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References

- [1] Cuadrat A, Chemical-looping combustion of coal using ilmenite as oxygen carrier. Doctoral Thesis at the University of Zaragoza. Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB-CSIC), 2012.
- [2] Condori O, García-Labiano F, de Diego LF, Izquierdo MT, Abad A, Adánez J, Biomass chemical looping gasification for syngas production using ilmenite as oxygen carrier in a 1.5 kW_{th} unit, Chem Eng J 405 (2021) 126679.
- [3] Leion H, Lyngfelt A, Johansson M, Jerndal E, Mattisson T, The use of ilmenite as an oxygen carrier in chemical-looping combustion, Chem Eng Res Des 86 (2008) 1017–26.
- [4] Adánez J, Cuadrat A, Abad A, Gayán P, de Diego LF, García-Labiano F, Ilmenite activation during consecutive redox cycles in chemical-looping combustion, Energy Fuel 24 (2010) 1402–13.
- [5] Pröll T, Mayer K, Bolhàr-Nordenkamp J, Kolbitsch P, Mattisson T, Lyngfelt A, Hofbauer H, Natural minerals as oxygen carrier for chemical looping combustion in a dual circulating fluidized bed system. GHGT-9. Energy Procedia 1 (2009) 27–34.
- [6] Abad A, Pérez-Vega R, de Diego LF, García-Labiano F, Gayán P, Adánez J, Design and operation of a 50 kW_{th} Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) unit for solid fuels, App Energy 157 (2015) 295-303.
- [7] Simell P, Ståhlberg P, Kurkela E, Albrecht J, Deutsch S, Sjöström K, Provisional protocol for the sampling and analysis of tar and particulates in the gas from large scale biomass gasifiers. Version 1998, Biomass Bioenerg 18 (2000) 19–38.
- [8] Condori O, de Diego LF, García-Labiano F, Izquierdo MT, Abad A, Adánez J, Syngas Production in a 1.5 kW_{th} Biomass Chemical Looping Gasification Unit Using Fe and Mn Ores as the Oxygen Carrier, Energy Fuels 35 (2021) 17182-17196.
- [9] Samprón I, de Diego LF, García-Labiano F, Izquierdo MT, Optimization of synthesis gas production in the biomass chemical looping gasification process operating under auto-thermal conditions, Energy 226 (2021) 120317.
- [10] Ge H, Guo W, Shen L, Song T, Xiao J, Biomass gasification using chemical looping in a 25 kW_{th} reactor with natural hematite as oxygen carrier, Chem Eng J 286 (2016) 174–183.
- [11] Wei G, He F, Zhao Z, Huang Z, Zheng A, Zhao K, Li H, Performance of Fe-Ni bimetallic oxygen carriers for chemical looping gasification of biomass in a 10 kW_{th} interconnected circulating fluidised bed reactor, Int J Hydrog Energy 40 (2015) 16021–16032.
- [12] Abad A, Adánez J, Cuadrat A, García-Labiano F, Gayán P, de Diego LF, Kinetics of redox reactions of ilmenite for chemical-looping combustion, Chem Eng Sci 66, 4 (2011) 689-702